

LEARNING GRAMMAR AT THE LESSONS OF RUSSIAN AS A
FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11207500>

Abstract: This article discusses the methods of grammar learning at the lessons of Russian as a foreign language in the school environment. The study covers different approaches to teaching grammar, including traditional methods such as rules and exercises, as well as modern approaches including games, interactive exercises and integration of grammatical structures into authentic communicative situations.

Key words: Russian as a foreign language, grammar, teaching, lessons, school, methods, traditional methods, modern approaches, practical recommendations.

Russian is one of the most difficult languages in the world, so foreign learners have some difficulties when learning it. In order for Russian language teaching to be effective, the teacher should organise classes competently, taking into account typical difficulties arising in the course of the educational process.

Teaching Russian as a foreign language (hereinafter - RCT) is a very complex, but at the same time interesting process for both learners and teacher. For successful teaching it is necessary to study in detail various methods of teaching RCT, as well as to take into account the personal and cultural characteristics of students. It is important to note that a foreign language teacher should pay special attention to the communicative-teaching function, which determines the importance of building a training session on a communicative-speech basis and allows him/her to better interact with students.

Foreign-speaking learners often have various problems when learning Russian due to the complexity of the material being learnt. However, this issue also becomes the teacher's problem, as he/she needs to find the best way to explain complex, problematic language phenomena.

Problems in learning the Russian language can start at a very early stage when learning the alphabet and phonetics. Students need to memorise how each letter and each sound is pronounced. It is important to explain the features of hard and soft signs, because they do not have a sound, but are separating signs

and indicate the hardness or softness of the consonant sound in front of them. The peculiarities of Russian phonetics are a great difficulty for students, so the teacher should pay attention to this aspect and regularly conduct phonetic exercises, phonetic dictations, practice various exercises for training and placement of sounds. Students need to learn to distinguish sounds by ear, as there are certain difficulties in recognising a word by its sound. When studying phonetics, the teacher should be guided by the reproductive method of teaching, he/she should become a model of correct pronunciation of sounds, pronunciation of words.

At the initial stage of the lesson, students can train the articulatory apparatus by means of reading cursive phrases. The teacher should show an example of correct reading of a phrase-speech, taking into account accentological norms, intonation, tempo and syntagmatic accent [5].

Another difficult problem in learning Russian as a foreign language is the assimilation of grammatical laws and rules. Russian is an inflective language, i.e. the expression of grammatical meanings is dominated by word-formation with the help of inflections. Here special attention should be paid to declension (change of a word according to the grammatical categories of gender, number and case).

The case system of the Russian language causes special difficulties for foreign-speaking learners. According to N. S. Vlasova, a methodologist in Russian language teaching, the sequential introduction of grammar depends on the frequency of use of certain grammatical forms in the language. In this case, the sequence of introducing and studying cases is dictated by the fact which of the case meanings occur more often in the language. Pupils are offered to study a model with a subject expressed by one or another case of a noun or a personal pronoun: Here is the table, it is here. Where is the book? It is there. After that it is advisable to introduce first non-transitive verbs with -a (to play, to dine, etc.), then adjectives are given to express determinative relations, since possessive pronouns are already mastered on the models (my, mine, mine, yours...). After studying the model with the nominative case of the noun (in the sense of the subject) and personal pronouns, the model with the prepositional case (in the sense of place - where?) is introduced, denoting the location of the object: The book on the table. The task is in the book. This corresponds to the frequency of use of the prepositional case in this very meaning. The introduction for the study of verbs in the construction is determined by which of the case meanings is studied at this stage [2].

The lexical diversity of the Russian language is presented in thematic groups, e.g.: "Family", "City", "Weather", "Time", "Body parts", "Professions", etc. [1]. When studying vocabulary, the teacher should constantly use various visual aids (illustrations, slide presentations, video clips), and active work with the dictionary should be organised.

The effectiveness of learning Russian words can be achieved by finding the lexical equivalent in the native language. It is more appropriate to carry out such work on the basis of a ready-made text according to the following plan: translation of a Russian text into the native language - retelling of the same text in Russian. It is important to take into account that such work can be effective if students have the necessary vocabulary of Russian words. Such tasks can also be organised with the help of guiding questions on the text. In order to ensure that foreign-language learners are more interested in learning Russian, it is necessary to use teaching materials containing the following information: information about the language, history, culture, way of life, traditions of Russia, as well as information relevant to the learners' professional field and their interests. When teaching Russian as a foreign language, the teacher should take into account the national-cultural, individual-psychological and personal characteristics of students, and his creative individuality should contribute to the best conduct of classes.

In modern methodology of Russian language teaching there is an opinion that the basis of teaching Russian as a foreign language is the scheme of relationships "teacher - learner - means of learning", which is defined as pedagogical communication and implies partnership of a foreign learner and a teacher. The teacher of Russian as a foreign language should not only support the learner in solving educational tasks, but also help him/her to better adapt to a foreign culture, to understand and accept new social patterns. A teacher of Russian as a foreign language should be an open and friendly person who is able to positively influence and interest students.

Foreign language learners especially note the teacher's behaviour in his professional pedagogical sphere, namely in the classroom, in the course of which he most clearly reveals his creative personality. Educational work with students and extracurricular communication with them are of great importance in language acquisition. Conducting non-traditional classes (absentee excursions, discussions, games), organising excursions and cultural events dedicated to significant dates, contribute to the rapid adaptation of students to the language environment.

Thus, intensive and quality learning of Russian as a foreign language is impossible without certain communication barriers, which is a particular difficulty in the learning process. However, with a detailed study of the similarities and differences of cultures, this problem becomes quite solvable. When organising the learning process, the teacher should take into account the probable difficulties of learning material assimilation by students and pay special attention to each problem so that foreign-language learners can fully use the learnt material in the communicative sphere.

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